

Numerical Study on Structural Performance of Polyurethane Foam-Filled Built-Up Cold-Formed Steel Members

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ABSTRACT

Cold-formed steel (CFS) built-up sections have over time, become more preferred over single CFS sections due to the substantial improvements they offer to the overall structural performance. CFS is widely used in pre-engineered buildings (PEB) as cladding and roof members due to its lightweight and thermal properties. Introducing CFS with Polyurethane foam (PUF) improves thermal performance and structural behaviour when compared to the same configuration of conventional built-up sections. In the existing literature, the combination of CFS and PUF is not thoroughly explored or discussed. In this study, numerical investigations using the commercially available finite element (FE) package ABAQUS have been carried out on a bare frame with and without PUF. The objective of the study is to analyse the difference in the load-carrying capacities and the failure pattern subjected to static loads. The results are compared with the available experimental and analytical studies and are found to be in good agreement.

Keywords: *Cold-formed steel, CFS, Polyurethane foam, Finite element modeling*

1 INTRODUCTION

Cold-rolled items became increasingly favored during the 1920s and have seen a surge in utilization over the past two decades due to their advantageous combination of high strength relative to weight and ease of handling. Since cold-rolled sections exhibit high malleability, they can be transformed into various geometric cross-sections. Assembled into structural elements, these cold-formed steel profiles find application in constructions, serving as components loaded in bending, axial force, or combined loadings. Moreover, the incorporation of CFS with materials such as PUF, known for their lightweight nature and excellent thermal insulation properties, can enhance the structural efficacy of the element. PEB structures with PUF insulation would offer notable benefits, particularly for cold storage yards, industrial office buildings, and defense structures situated at high altitudes, where adherence to climatic conditions is crucial. Initially, investigations focused on sandwich panels as building cladding because of their numerous benefits, including enhanced structural effectiveness, straightforward assembly, mass-production potential, and thermal insulation properties (1, 2).

The research on the behaviour of such built-up elements combined with PUF, to a certain extent, limited. Studying both the constituents and the overall configuration will inevitably exert a significant influence on the performance of assembled elements. This study will focus on the numerical investigation of the experimental study carried out by R. Sagadevan and B. N. Rao (3). The geometric specifications of the study are shown in the Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Details of Bare frame (Specimen B1) & Bare frame with PUF infill (Specimen B2)

2 FINITE ELEMENT INVESTIGATION

2.1 General

The finite element software ABAQUS (2021) (4) was employed to conduct numerical simulations of both the bare frame and PUF-filled sections. Throughout the finite element analysis (FEA), the exact cross-sectional measurements of the specimens were utilized. Two forms of FEA were conducted: initially, an eigenvalue analysis was employed to ascertain the buckling modes of the built-up columns. This linear-elastic analysis was executed using the Linear Perturbation-Buckle procedure found within the ABAQUS library. Subsequently, a load-displacement nonlinear analysis was performed using the Riks algorithm, also available within the ABAQUS library. The initial geometric imperfections and material non-linearities were included in the numerical modeling.

2.2 Element type, mesh size, and material model

Each component of the bare frame, including angle sections, profile sheets, rectangular tube sections, and channel sections, were represented using four-node shell elements with reduced integration (S4R). In the case of PUF-filled sections, the foam was modeled using solid 3D continuum elements (C3D8R), in addition to the bare frame section.

A mesh size of 20mm x 20mm was employed for achieving model convergence for all S4R elements, as well as for the C3D8R elements, as shown in Fig. 2. The cold rolled steel material non-linearity was incorporated in the finite element model by specifying 'true' values of stresses and strains as reported by Ananthi, G.B.G. et al (5). A crushable foam model (available in the ABAQUS library) was used to model the foam material by incorporating the material properties obtained by the experimental works carried out by Tuwair et al (6).

Fig. 2. Typical FE mesh a) Bareframe; b) PUF-filled section

2.3 Connection modeling

The tack weld connection linking different sections of the bare frame was simulated using the Tie constraint. Specifically, the profile sheet and angle sections were partitioned to allow selection of only the overlapping regions for the tie constraint, as depicted in Fig. 3.

PUF-filled specimen, the PUF infill material is specified as the host region and the bare frame is specified as embedded region. The cover sheet of the PUF-filled specimens is secured using self-tapping screws, represented by the MPC beam connector element.

Fig. 3. Utilization of the Tie constraint to replicate welded connections.

2.4 Boundary conditions and load application

Pin-ended boundary conditions were implemented for both specimens. In the case of the bare frame specimen and the PUF-filled specimen, reference points were established at their centroids. Multi-point connector (MPC) beam elements were then connected through these reference points to the ends of the members, and axial loads were subsequently applied on the reference points accordingly, as illustrated in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, respectively.

Fig. 4. MPC beam constraint applied at the ends of bare frame

Fig. 5. MPC beam constraint applied at the ends of the PUF-filled section

2.5 Modeling of initial geometric imperfections

Local, distortional, and global buckling behaviour of CFS depends on number of factors such as web-to-thickness ratio, width of flange-to-thickness ratio, and slenderness about the x-axis and y-axis. Hence, local and global buckling modes obtained from the eigenvalue analysis were superimposed for accurate FEA.

In this study the magnitude of the imperfection for global and local buckling were considered as $L/1000$ (L is the length of the specimen) and $0.34t$ (t is the thickness), respectively, following the recommendations of Schafer and Pekoz (1998) (7).

3 OBSERVATIONS

The experimental research carried out by R. Sagadevan and B. N. Rao (3) on the bare frame, with the corresponding FE model developed for this study, is depicted in Fig. 6. Furthermore, the PUF-filled specimen (3), illustrated in Fig. 7, along with its corresponding FE model developed, is also presented. An axial compression test was performed on the bare frame, and its failure pattern was compared with the FE model, as depicted in Fig. 8. Moreover, an axial compression test was carried out on the PUF-filled sections, and the resulting failure pattern was compared in Fig. 9. Observations revealed that the axial load capacity of specimen B2 (with PUF filling) is nearly double that of specimen B1 (bare frame). The rise in load-bearing capacity is credited to the PUF filling, which aids in preventing premature localized failure.

a)

b)

Fig. 6. a) Experiment setup of the bare frame; b) FE Model of the bare frame

a)

b)

Fig. 7. a) Experimental set-up of PUF-filled specimen; b) FE model of PUF-filled specimen

LVDTs were placed at one meter interval from the support to measure the lateral displacement. For the bare frame, the load-displacement curve from the FE analysis is in good agreement with the experimental results as shown in Fig. 10. In case of the PUF-filled section the load-displacement curve from FE analysis is comparable to the experimental results in the elastic region and deviation is observed beyond this elastic limit as shown in the Fig. 10. The FE results for the PUF-filled section needs to be refined.

a)

b)

Fig. 8. Failure pattern a) Test; b) FEA

a)

b)

Fig. 9. Failure pattern of PUF-filled section a) Test; b) FEA

4 DISCUSSION

The structural performance of cold-formed steel bare frame and frame filled with Polyurethane foam (PUF) as infill material is investigated. The increase in the axial load-carrying capacity of the cold-formed PUF-filled sections when compared with the bare frame section concludes that the PUF is contributing to the strength by delaying the premature local buckling failure.

Fig. 10. Load-Displacement curve a) Bare frame; b) PUF-filled Section

5 CONCLUSIONS

The structural performance of cold-formed steel bare frame and frame filled with Polyurethane foam (PUF) as infill material is investigated.

- 1) The axial compression capacity of the specimen filled with PUF (B2) is almost twice that of the bare frame specimen (B1).
- 2) PUF prevents the premature local failure observed in specimen B1, but not in specimen B2.

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